

RETHINKING THE ROMAN EPIGRAPHY OF MERCHANDISE: A METAPRAGMATIC APPROACH¹

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*“Knowing how to communicate in writing is one thing,
doing so is another”²*

I. PRELIMINARY REMARKS

The epigraphy of merchandise focuses on inscriptions written on artifacts used in commerce, such as amphorae, barrels, and ingots. For these writings, it is possible to distinguish techniques employed (such as painting, scraffitting,³ or chiselling) and locations on the objects. The life cycle of the artifact is the path followed by merchandise from the moment it is produced (e.g., in the kiln, on the estate) until it arrives

¹ The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007–2013)/ERC grant agreement n° 339123. Abbreviations: *CIL* = *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum*; *D.* = The Digest of Justinian; *Dressel 20* = H. Dressel, “Ricerche sul Monte Testaccio” (N 13); *P.Bad.* = *Veröffentlichungen aus den badischen Papyrus-Sammlungen*; *P.Oxy.* = *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri*; *P.Stras.* = *Griechische Papyrus der Kaiserlichen Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek zu Strassburg*; *SEG* = *Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum*.

² R. MacMullen, “The Epigraphic Habit in the Roman Empire,” *American Journal of Philology* 103.3 (1983): 2.

³ In the artifacts, graffiti appear always incised in the material. A general definition of graffiti has been recently proposed by M. Andrieu, *Graffites en Gaule Lyonnaise: contribution à l’étude des inscriptions gravées sur vaisselle céramique: Corpus d’Autun, Chartres et Sens* (Autun: Mergoïl, 2017): 31–32, indicating that they are incised inscriptions, in cursive calligraphy, that reflect an individual and spontaneous message.

at one destination (e.g., the port, the market, the shop). To that aim, I have built a model in which the different techniques employed help trace the itinerary of the merchandise traded overseas from one port of departure to its destination. For this study, the port-context relates to the administration, organization, and jurisdiction performed by the authorities at the Mediterranean ports during the high Roman Empire (first–third centuries C.E.).⁴ In this period, Roman hegemony was established along the Mediterranean, and the ports located on their shores were growing and hosting commercial traffic from all corners of the Empire.⁵

This paper examines the ways in which the techniques and the language employed on these inscribed commercial goods provide information regarding their use as merchandise. I connect the materiality of these objects with Roman law, by shifting the focus from traditional epigraphic analysis to the means by which inscriptions were created, shaped, and used as commercial tools throughout the Mediterranean. I argue that these features—the language and technique employed for writing, as well as the visual arrangement of words on the artifact—are metadiscursive phenomena that shaped the communicative function of the inscription. Though I will generally speak of Roman merchandise, my focus will be essentially on the Latin world, despite the fact that the evidence of Greek-inscribed merchandise points to use of the same techniques for similar processes.⁶

A better understanding of the inscription’s communicative function, in turn, allows us to achieve a better reconstruction of the artifacts’ commercial itinerary and context inside the cycles of production and distribution. The description in this paper of the distribution cycle, and the different aims of the techniques used in the inscriptions provide a deep insight into the traders’ minds. The codes and abbreviations employed

⁴ This approach benefits from the spatial turn, a theoretical approach that in the last years has been used in order to understand spaces of justice, public or domestic locations. See, for example: A. M. Riggsby, “‘Public’ and ‘Private’ in Roman Culture: The Case of the Cubiculum,” *JRA* 10 (1997): 36–56; L. Bablitz, *Actors and Audience in the Roman Courtroom* (London: Duckworth, 2007); F. De Angelis, *Spaces of Justice in the Roman World* (Leiden: Brill, 2010); R. Farber, *Römische Gerichtsorte: Räumliche Dynamiken von Jurisdiktion im Imperium Romanum* (München: Beck, 2014); K. Tuori and L. Nissin, *Public and Private in the Roman House and Society* (JRA Supplements; Oxford: JRA, 2015); A. Russell, *The Politics of Public Space in Republican Rome* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 2016).

⁵ See for example J. Rougé, *Recherches sur l’organisation du commerce maritime en Méditerranée sous l’Empire romain* (Paris: S.E.V.P.E.N., 1966): 121–146; S. J. Keay, *Rome, Portus and the Mediterranean* (Rome: British School at Rome, 2012).

⁶ For example, M. Lang, *The Athenian Agora: Graffiti and Dipinti* (Athens: American School at Athens, 1976): 55–86.

indicate the awareness of these subjects of the pragmatic functions of these inscriptions.⁷ In this way, the meanings of these inscriptions and their techniques were metapragmatic, as applied to an audience of traders and associated people.

II. THE *CORPUS* AND ASSOCIATED EPIGRAPHIC RECORD

The analysis has targeted a wide range of inscribed commercial artifacts in order to study and compare their epigraphic records. One of the elements that speaks most strongly of the relatively high level of integration of the Roman Empire was the high flow of goods that took place along different Mediterranean areas. Long distances and cultural differences made necessary the existence of some common practices, protected by the law of the Empire that enhanced commercial networks.⁸ The recurrent techniques (see fig. 1, Pl. XVI) and language used in the inscriptions prove the existence of these common practices. Figs. A and B from the appendix display the sample of the artifacts and the labelling of their inscriptions that have been used to build the model of commercial procedures outlined in fig. 2 (Pl. XVI) below. In addition, the chart of fig. C (appendix) displays the labels of the inscriptions considered in this study.

⁷ The explanation of how Roman practice lines up only approximately with any lexicon, expressing shared knowledge, is underlined in the work of A. Riggsby, *Mosaics of Knowledge: Representing Information in the Roman World* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., forthcoming). That assertion was previously mentioned by G. Woolf, "Literacy or Literacies in Rome?" in *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome* (W. A. Johnson and H. N. Parker, eds.; Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2009): 57.

⁸ T. Terpstra, "Roman Law, Transaction Costs and the Roman Economy," in *Pistoi dia tèn technèn: Bankers, Loans and Archives in the Ancient World: Studies in Honour of Raymond Bogaert* (K. Verboven, K. Vandorpe, and V. Chankowski, eds.; Leuven: Peeters, 2008): 345–369, who analyses the case of the wax tablets from the *Sulpicii* archive, highlighting how the complex legal system had a real impact on daily life.

Figure 1: Examples of different inscribed artifacts and techniques. From left to right: painted fish sauce amphora from Almeria;⁹ barrel stave with fire marks from Vindolanda;¹⁰ graffiti in amphora found in Magdalensberg (Germany).¹¹

The evidence remaining in the diverse areas of the Mediterranean has allowed us to trace a model of the pattern of the practice of inscribing artifacts. For example painted inscriptions (*tituli picti*) are not always preserved in the material record, and sometimes are found in a fragmentary state that make them impossible to read. However, a recent study of Pompeii's amphora pile from the *bottega del garum* demonstrated some commonalities, such as that fish sauce vessels were usually and individually inscribed before setting sail.¹²

Such a consideration for the execution of the marks and writings on these objects can elucidate the economic processes underlying these economic networks. I have also considered the stamps (e.g., fig. 2), which correspond to the production of the container, and help us understand the different events happening during its commercial life cycle. I will argue that the technique employed can help trace different moments in the distribution path of the artifact. In addition, the calligraphy of these inscriptions allows us to see if they were written in different moments by diverse people.

⁹ B. Liou and E. Rodriguez Almeida, "Les inscriptions peintes des amphores du Pecio Gandolfo (Almería)," *Mélanges de L'école Française de Rome. Antiquité* 112.1 (2000): 12, fig. 3.

¹⁰ Barrel stave found at Vindolanda in 2016 ("Wooden Treasures Unearthed at Vidolanda," *Vindolanda Charitable Trust*, 28 June 2016, http://www.vindolanda.com/_blog/press-releases/post/wooden-treasures-unearthed-at-vindolanda/. Accessed 22 Jan. 2019.

¹¹ V. Maier-Maidl, *Stempel und Inschriften auf Amphoren vom Magdalensberg: Wirtschaftliche Aspekte* (Kärnten: Landesmuseums für Kärnten, 1992): 111, fig. 1:2.

¹² D. Bernal et al., "Un contexto excepcional en Pompeya: la Pila de Anforas de la Bottega del Garum (I, 12, 8). Avance de un estudio interdisciplinar," *Rei Cretariae Romanae Fautorum Acta* 43 (2014): 231. A procedure that is also perceivable in P. Bad. 2.43.

Figure 2: Dressel 20 seal impressions and inscriptions from the Severan period (Second half 2nd c. C.E. and first half 3rd c. C.E.).¹³

Discussions of linguistic pragmatics—that is, discussions of what language does in a particular context—are metapragmatic, because they describe the meaning of language as action. So “metapragmatic” in this paper refers to the semiotically informed linguistic anthropology of Michael Silverstein,¹⁴ and outlines how the effects and conditions of the language used on Roman commercial artifacts become objects of discourse. Moreover, metapragmatic signalling allows participants to construe what is going on in an interaction. In this case, I have used this approach to understand the epigraphy of merchandise as interacting in different ways with the parties involved in their distributive itinerary. With such an approach, I aim to: (1) specify under which conditions a specific kind of language is used. In this case, the context conditioning

¹³ H. Dressel, “Ricerche sul Monte Testaccio,” *Annali dell’Istituto di Corrispondenza Archeologica* (1878): 118–192.

¹⁴ M. Silverstein. “The Limits of Awareness: Sociolinguistic Working Paper Number 84,” in *Linguistic Anthropology. A Reader* (A. Duranti, ed.; Malden: Wiley-Blackwell, 2001): 382–401; idem, “Metapragmatic Discourse and Metapragmatic Function,” in *Reflexive Language Reported Speech and Metapragmatics* (J. A. Lucy, ed.; Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 1993): 33–58.

the language refers to the different events that happened during the distribution itinerary of the merchandise from one port to other; (2) signal the kind of event occurring within the different procedures happening on the distribution path (model fig. 4); (3) and link the absence of use of this sort of language to the different events or conditions. Silverstein indicated that “the text can act as an artefact,”¹⁵ which in this case fits perfectly with the functions of the inscribed objects; and it might even seem redundant if we suggest that we are talking about texts inscribed on artifacts. What makes commercial epigraphy a textual artifact are the circumstances governing the object that motivate its users to inscribe it; and consequently, the act of making denotes a particular signification for the people involved in the commercial cycle.

Therefore, I conceive pragmatics as dealing with the techniques and the language used for the inscriptions, the context of writing and the communicative principles that connect one and the other. These connections enable participants to interact successfully with these artifacts and understand what was reflected in these writings. In this case, the inscriptions worked within the context of the distribution of merchandise, and among people who read and worked with these objects in their daily life. The daily practice of trade implied that its participants, who shared frames of knowledge and mind,¹⁶ consequently understood the meaning of these encoded inscriptions. Signs functioning metapragmatically have an inherent “framing,” meaning that they were employed in a particular context with participants who were familiar with them in order to deliver a message effectively.¹⁷

The inscriptions could be painted, stamped, scraffited, or marked with fire. The commercial itinerary of an artifact, which resulted in several marks on the objects, was generally governed by the kind of technique used. The repetition on the use of diverse marking techniques according to the event and stage in the distribution cycle was known to the traders, who understood the meanings of the marking techniques and were able to interact with them. The diverse methods used to inscribe the vessels conform to discursive interactions, indicating the social circumstances behind the inscription. They allowed an interaction with the subject reading it, and therefore fulfilled the purpose that the writings sought to achieve.

¹⁵ Ibid., 38.

¹⁶ W. Bublitz, and A. Hübler, “Introducing Metapragmatics in Use,” in *Metapragmatics in Use* (W. Bublitz, and A. Hübler, eds; Pragmatics & Beyond N.S., 165; Amsterdam: Benjamin, 2007): 5–6.

¹⁷ Silverstein, *The Limits of Awareness* (N 14): 34.

The aim of these actions was threefold: (1) it allowed long-distance communication amongst trading parties. The shortened language used repeatedly on merchandise acted as an encoded formulary that allowed the different parties working in trade to understand the features of the product and its patterns of distribution; (2) it stated the relationship of ownership of the merchandise,¹⁸ the liability of the parties involved in the sale of the object or the transport of it; (3) and finally, these inscribed objects could be used as proof (*probatio*)¹⁹ to enforce the terms of an agreement in case one party did not fulfill the conditions agreed upon. For example, several texts²⁰ describe the particularities of wine sale, in which a tasting can be arranged between the parties to confirm that the wine conformed to the features agreed and inscribed on the vessel (e.g., *vinum mulsum*, sweet wine).

¹⁸ A. Cooley, *The Cambridge Manual of Latin Epigraphy* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 2012): 82–103.

¹⁹ The word *probatio* points to an approbatory statement, delivered by the magistrate or another subject with authority (e.g., a customer), in connection to a document or object presented for examination. In the sale of goods, many purchases were subject to probation to check if the quality of the good was as agreed, and acceptable as the product. For further reading, see, for example, G. Geraci, “Mensura, pondus e probatio di stato nel rifornimento granario di Roma imperiale (e di Costantinopoli),” in *Politica, retorica e simbolismo del primato: Roma e Costantinopoli (secoli IV–VII). Atti Del Convegno Internazionale (Catania, 4–7 Ottobre 2001). Omaggio a Rosario Soraci* (E. Febronia, ed.; Catania: CULC, 2004): 155–181; D. Vera, “Un’iscrizione sulle distribuzioni pubbliche di vino a Roma (*CIL*, VI, 1785 = 31931),” in *Studi in onore Di Francesco Grelle* (M. Silvestrini, T. Spagnuolo Vigorita and G. Volpe eds.; Bari: Edipuglia, 2006): 303–317, and also D.18.1.34.5; Philostratus, *Vita Apollonii* VI.12.

²⁰ Cato, *de agri cultura*, 148; Philostratus, *Vita Apollonii* VI.12; *CIL*.VI.1785 = 31931; D.18.1.34.5; D.18.6.1pr.; D.18.6.4.1; D.18.6.16. R. Yaron. “Sale of Wine,” in *Studies in the Roman Law of Sale: Studies Dedicated to the Memory of Francis de Zulueta* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 1959): 71–77; B. W. Frier. “Roman Law and the Wine Trade: The Problem of ‘Vinegar Sold As Wine’,” *Zeitschrift Der Savigny-Stiftung für Rechtsgeschichte. Romanistische Abteilung* 100 (1983): 257–295.; G. Thür, “Rechtsfragen des Weinkaufs,” in *Akten des 21. Internationalen Papyrologenkongresses Berlin 1995, II* (B. Kramer, ed.; Archiv für Papyrusforschung, Beiheft 3; Stuttgart: Teubner, 1997): 967–975; E. Jakob, “Gaius kommentiert die Papyri? Vertragsklauseln im Weinkauf,” *Symposion 1995* (G. Thür and J. Velissaropoulos-Karakostas, eds.; Cologne: Böhlau, 1997): 313–324; A. Tchernia, “La vente au vin,” in *Mercati permanenti e mercati periodici nel mondo romano* (Elio Lo Cascio, ed.; Bari: Edipuglia, 2000); E. Jakob, *Risikomanagement beim Weinkauf: Periculum und Praxis im Imperium Romanum* (Munich: Beck, 2009); E. Santamato, “Il termine probatio tra retorica, storia e diritto,” *Talia Dixit* 7 (2012): 31–71.

III. PROVIDING CONTEXT TO THE INSCRIPTIONS: LIFE CYCLE OF THE ARTIFACTS

Commercial artifacts never stand still, are never inert. Their existence is always embedded in a multitude of contexts governing their distribution.²¹ I would like to highlight the ontological approach to interpreting merchandise. The different human interactions on a given object can be acknowledged on the ontograph detailed in fig. 3 below. An ontograph depicts the ways of being and becoming of an artifact, and so it outlines how an object acquires a different status through the human interactions coping with it.²² An ontograph constitutes a legend that introduces types and relationships among individuals, objects, and their interactions in a given situation.²³

Figure 3: Ontograph detailing the human interactions for a container. The right square indicates who was in contact with the merchandise, inscribing, transporting, or trading with it.

²¹ This is also the approach of the book of C. Knappett, *An Archaeology of Interaction Network Perspectives on Material Culture and Society* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2011).

²² I. Bogost. *Alien Phenomenology, or What It's Like to Be a Thing* (Minneapolis: Univ. of Minnesota, 2012): 35–60.

²³ T. Kuhn. "How to Evaluate Controlled Natural Languages," in *Pre-Proceedings of the Workshop on Controlled Natural Language (CNL 2009)*, CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Vol. 448 (2009).

These objects are meaningful only in relation to conflicts, negotiations, and appropriations²⁴ taking place during their distribution. Transformations on the significance of these artifacts for the subjects interacting with them can happen when objects change ownership and movement (shipping) that produces inscriptions denoting the different situations through which they pass and the participants involved. I am using here the concept-metaphor of the itinerary, which is necessary to understand the transformations that happened to the object during the commercial path and materialised in the inscriptions.

The model of fig. 4 describes the circumstances in which the inscriptions are created by tracking the different procedures in which the artifact is involved from its point of departure until its delivery to the final customer. This model has been built upon the evidence of the inscriptions with the help of other iconographic, legal (e.g., *Tabulae Pompeianae Sulpiciorum*),²⁵ literary (e.g., Phil. *Vita ap.*), papyrological (e.g., P.Stras. III 184), and epigraphic evidence (e.g., monumental epigraphy).²⁶

Figure 4: Commercial itinerary of the artifacts involved in trade overseas.

²⁴ That phrasing has been used also to refer to cultural artifacts by H. P. Hahn and H. Weiss, “Introduction: Biographies, Travels and Itineraries of Things,” in *Mobility, Meaning & Transformations of Things. Shifting Contexts of Material Culture through Time and Space* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2013): 1; also in the recent publication of A. Van Oyen and M. Pitts, *Materialising Roman Histories* (Oxford: Oxbow, 2017).

²⁵ G. Camodeca, *Tabulae Pompeianae sulpiciorum (TPSulp.)*. Ed critica (Roma: Quasar, 1999).

²⁶ E.g., *CIL*.III.14165; *CIL*.II.1180.

The procedures indicated in fig. 4 were not unique to just one Roman port in a specific area. When other regions of the Roman world are considered, regardless of the product meant to be traded by means of these artifacts, many of the distributing steps were common there too. There would have been some geographic variation, but overall the activities governing trade would have been similar across the Roman world.²⁷ These procedures were necessary to keep trade routes running smoothly on the different coasts of the Empire. Every port has to be seen as a particular place with unique infrastructures, particular customs systems, and divergent jurisdiction managing them. From these differences, a common framework of law emerges that governs the procedures taking place for sale, control, transportation, and storage of the cargo. However, while we acknowledge the importance of the multi-legalism and multiculturalism present in the diverse areas of the Mediterranean, this work will present a model based on classical western Roman law.²⁸ That model provides a unitary legal focus based on the law developed in the city of Rome to understand how trade was managed at the different Mediterranean ports. As with every model, it leaves aside some particularities that inevitably occur due to the diversity of cultures composing the Roman Empire. However, this model appears as a general framework of action with an underlying variety of practices that characterize the diversity of the Mediterranean.

These procedures do not always leave inscribed traces on the artifacts, which is one reason why the evidence of iconography, or other written and material sources is still needed.²⁹ The use of the model of the cycle

²⁷ This approach is also considered for amphora production in the Roman world by S. Gallimore, "Amphora Production in the Roman World: A View from the Papyrus," *The Bulletin of the American Society of Papyrologists* 47 (2010): 155–184. The author builds a case study about Roman wine amphora and creates a model to understand amphora production in a broader perspective.

²⁸ Meaning the legal system developed mainly in Rome, including the legal developments spanning the western parts of the Empire's capital, and which was extended to the western and eastern parts of the Empire, where it coped differently with the other legal traditions, which were in force in these areas. See G. Kantor, "Greek Law under the Romans," in *The Oxford Handbook of Ancient Greek Law* (M. Harris and M. Canevaro, eds.; Oxford, Oxford Univ., 2015). The Classical period of Roman law provides the best comprehensive framework of the development of Roman law, and it became a model for later generations of legal actors. The classical period stretched from about the last century of the Roman Republic to the end of the Principate (284 C.E.).

²⁹ See for example the *tesserae* indicating the payment of the *Quadragesima Galliarum* (XLGALL [IARUM] IMP [ERATOR] SS) found in the ancient port of Marseille, A. Hesnard, and J. France. "Une *statio* du quarantième des Gaules et les opérations commerciales dans le port romain de Marseille (place Jules-Verne)," *JRA* 8 (1995): 81, fig. 3.

of procedures of ports helps us to understand their peculiar traces with the help of these procedures that happened similarly in the different ports of the Mediterranean.

From the itinerary described in fig. 4 and the interactions described in the ontograph of fig. 3, I have also created a model of when and where the different techniques were employed on the merchandise (fig. 5).

Figure 5: Techniques and their use inside the cycle of distribution of artifacts.

From this diagram, five main locations can be appointed, where these functions took place and the objects could be inscribed:

(1) The kiln, estate, or workshop where the artifact was manufactured by a potter, filled and sealed by the people owning the produce on the estate and inscribed by the merchant. There the merchant wrote on the artifact the necessary details for the transport and sale of the object (e.g., P. Bad. 2.43; D.18.6.2pr.). Sometimes the merchant can also own the ship and then takes care of the transport as well as of the sale, which consequently has an effect on the inscriptions.³⁰ In these places the artifact was stamped (vessel, ingot, and barrel) or marked with fire (barrel), indicating the name of the kiln where the vessel was produced. There, the container was filled with the product, sealed (stamped with the name of the owner), and painted to indicate details about the product or ownership.

³⁰ A. Héron de Villefosse, *Deux armateurs narbonnais: Sex. Fadius Secundus et P. Olitius Apollonius* (Paris: Impr. de Daupley-Gouverneur, 1915).

Also graffiti written on the containers could indicate the initial of the potter, indicating for how many pots he had to be paid.³¹

(2) The port of departure where the goods were loaded into a ship. Here the shipper, who takes care of the transport could write some information on the artifact in case there is any change in the itinerary initially agreed by merchant and shipper. The owner of the ship (*exercitor*)³² could act as shipper, and also be the master of the ship or appoint another person to perform that role (e.g., D.14.1.1.1; D.44.7.5.6). If the vessels were not already marked, they could be painted and counted at this stage (P.Oxy. 43.3111 and P.Bad. 2.43). The port could also be a place for transshipment. If the cargo passed from one shipper to another, then the goods could be re-inscribed, indicating the liability of the new carrier in charge within the framework of lease and hire. The ship carrying the goods could change its itinerary, or the goods could be transhipped to another boat. Such an action resulted in marks on the vessels, indicating names written with a different hand that correspond to the new shipper in charge of transport. This happens with some cases found in the context of the river system of the Rhone, and it is connected with the liability of the shipper to carry the goods safely to the destination.³³

(3) The port of destination where the goods were inspected and handed to the final customer. Here the officer, acting on behalf of the Roman authorities, inspected the merchandise and the payment of the taxes. That control could lead to writing on the artifacts as they were inspected,³⁴ registered, taxed, or before storing them in warehouses or handing them to their owner (e.g., *Lex Portorii Asiae*).³⁵ At the port of destination, the

³¹ V. F. Gavini, "Il relitto 'E' del mariposa (Alguero)," *Erentzas* 1 (2011): 240.

³² The best work for understanding the relation among the different roles involved in trade and transport is J. J. Aubert, *Business Managers in Ancient Rome* (Leiden: Brill, 1994).

³³ S. Martin-Kilcher, "Lucius Urattius Verecundus, Négociant à la fin du 1er siècle, et sa merchandise découverte à Mayence," in *Vivre, produire et échanger: reflets méditerranéens. Mélanges offerts à Bernard Liou* (Montagnac: Mergoïl, 2002): 343–353; M. Poux, "Du vin marseillais pour Staius Regillus: un témoignage du commerce rhodanien et de la colonisation des campagnes entre Lyon et Vienne," *Archaeologia Mosellana* 9 (2014): 410; T. Silvino et al., "Tituli picti e tutti quanti. Nouvelles inscriptions peintes sur amphores dans la vallée du Rhone," *SFECAG, Actes du Congrès de Nyon* (2015): 650; D. Djaoui, "Circulation et diffusion des marchandises depuis le delta du Rhône," in *Potins et pots de vins. Échange, commerce et transport vers la Gaule du Nord* (P. Cattelain and A. Leblon, eds.; Treignes: Cedarc, 2017): 93–95.

³⁴ J. France and J. Nelis-Clement, "Tout en bas de l'empire. Les stations militaires et douanières lieux de contrôle et de représentation du pouvoir," in *La statio. Archéologie d'un lieu de pouvoir dans l'empire romain* (Bordeaux: Ausonius, 2014): 222–223.

³⁵ M. Cottier, M. Crawford, and C. Crowther et al., *The Customs Law of Asia* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2008).

goods were controlled by the authorities for the payment of customs³⁶ or registration, and handed to the final customer or stored in a warehouse. Here we can find seals,³⁷ used to register the arrivals and address them to the right place. That happened especially in the case of goods destined for public supply or public buildings (marble),³⁸ and painted inscriptions, also indicating issues concerning the registry of the goods.

(4) The warehouses where the goods were stored waiting to be shipped to other places³⁹ or for sale. The latter is especially noticeable with the ingots, which were easily sealable and needed to be used as ballast, thus depending on the cargoes, some shippers sold them at the port, and they were kept on these warehouses until they were sold again.⁴⁰

(5) The market or the shop where the goods were sold or the warehouse where the goods were stored. At these sites, the customer bought the merchandise and was entitled to enforce the contract if there were features described in the agreement that were not fulfilled by the product (e.g., D.18.1.34.5). The market or the shop where the good was sold, where we can find either painted inscriptions witnessing details about the sale (e.g. *CIL.XV.4539*), or graffiti also indicating features of the good sold (e.g., *CIL.XIII.10008.43*)

The analysis of the evidence allows me to contextualize the different techniques, by relating one sort of writing to specific moments in

³⁶ When a ship arrived in harbor, its cargo had to be registered. Two separate taxes were levied on ships entering a harbor: harbor dues (municipal fees exacted for the use of harbors and their facilities) and customs fees (state taxes calculated *ad valorem*). See, for example, the Customs law of Asia (*monum. Ephesenum* 16–20 §6) or the Customs law of Caunus (*SEG.XIV.639*), see also Ch. Marek, *Die Inschriften von Kaunos* (München: Beck, 2006).

³⁷ A registration scene in which it is possible to see one subject with an item on his hand used for stamping the goods registered can be found in a relief found in Portus. See C. Pavolini, “L’edilizia commerciale e l’edilizia abitativa nel contesto di Ostia tardoantica,” in *Società e impero tardoantico II: Roma. Politica, economia, paesaggio urbano* (A. Giardina, ed.; Roma-Bari: Laterza, 1986): fig. 17.

³⁸ Several seals of marble with the faces of emperors have been found at Portus, as can be seen in E. Spagnoli, “Sigili plumbei e blocchi di Porto,” in *I marmi colorati della Roma imperial* (Venecia: Marsilio, 2002): 496; another seal has been recently (2017) found at Portus, in the context of the Palazzo Imperiale, which helps to set the artifact in context (forthcoming publication).

³⁹ J. Torres Costa, “*Ex Hor(reis) Had(rumetinis)*. À propos d’un titulus pictus mentionnant les entrepôts d’Hadrumetum au IIIe s. ap. J.-C.,” in *In Africa et in Hispania. Études sur l’huile africaine* (Jose Remesal Rodríguez, ed.; Barcelona: Instrumenta, 2007): 299–315.

⁴⁰ C. Rico, “Réflexions sur le commerce d’exportation des métaux à l’époque Romaine. La logique du stockage,” in *Horrea d’Hispanie et de la méditerranée romaine* (J. Aerce and B. Goffaux, eds.; Madrid: Casa de Velázquez, 2011): 41–64.

the distribution cycle. All these places make up the topography through which the artifacts passed. In each place the different operations and intentions of the parties generated a diverse record on the objects. The model involves three main functions: sale, inspection, and transport. Sale and transport are represented respectively by the contracts of sale and lease and hire, agreed upon by the parties involved in the distribution. The use of certain techniques at a specific moment and the repetition of the position of the writings reveals that some habits were used repeatedly. They were understood by the subjects involved in these procedures, who were also able to appreciate the abbreviated language employed on the artifacts.

IV. CODING COMMERCIAL MESSAGES. TECHNIQUES, LOCATION, AND LANGUAGE EMPLOYED IN THE INSCRIPTIONS

Multiple features constitute the material presentation of the epigraphic record of artifacts, including the relative positioning of the texts, the technique used in the inscription, and the message encoded in it. While visual primacy is not necessarily indicative of a texts' priority in the distributive path, when compounded with other features, it can illuminate the texts' relationships to one another. The table of fig. C (appendix) displays a model of the sorts of supports and techniques employed and the message conveyed by the text. The writings compose a formula, meaning that at least part of the information had to be readable for a specified length of time, possibly for the duration of the voyage, or following shipment, to ensure that it could be read at the destination.

At this point, I would like to introduce the concept of the "sense of audience," coined by Ramsay MacMullen.⁴¹ With this concept, the author

⁴¹ MacMullen (n 2): 246. The term has been broadly accepted in scholarship, stressing its importance in understanding imperial society and relating the concept to different focuses of study. See, for example: R. Saller and B. D. Shaw. "Tombstones and Roman Family Relations in the Principate: Civilians, Soldiers and Slaves," *JRS* 74 (1984): 124–156; J. C. Mann, "Epigraphic Consciousness," *JRS* 75.1 (1985): 204–206; G. Woolf, "Monumental Writing and the Expansion of Roman Society in the Early Empire," *JRS* 86.1 (1996): 22–39; A. Chaniotis. "From Communal Spirit to Individuality: The Epigraphic Habit in Hellenistic and Roman Crete," in *Creta romana e protobizantina. Atti del convegno internazionale, Heraklion, 23–30 september 2000* (Padova: Univ. di Padova, 2004): 75–87; J. P. Bodel, *Epigraphic Evidence: Ancient History from Inscriptions* (London: Routledge, 2001); R. Hingley, *Globalizing Roman Culture: Unity, Diversity and Empire* (London: Routledge, 2005); W. Ameling, "The Epigraphic Habit and the Jewish Diasporas of Asia Minor and Syria," in *From Hellenism to Islam: Cultural and Linguistic Change in the Roman Near*

argued that in the high Roman Empire, the number of Latin inscriptions apparently grew, but then dropped drastically, because of a close relationship between the epigraphic habit and Romanization. These inscriptions reflected the Roman identity of the writer and they would therefore be closely associated with Roman practices. Even if the author was talking about monumental inscriptions, the main thing is to recall that in the habit of inscribing, the people leaving these writings shared a knowledge of what these writings meant. In a similar way, people involved in trade shared a frame of knowledge about the meanings of the inscriptions and the techniques employed. When we appreciate a large monumental inscription, it seems clear that it aims to appeal to a large (literate) audience, who understood the abbreviations employed.⁴² In the case of the epigraphy of merchandize, the abbreviations were read in the context of trade, and consequently understood by the people involved in that activity. Thus they were using an encoded language which make them all part of something common: the world of trade in the Roman Empire.

To start with the case of the producer, their name appears written in the nominative case, or indicated only with their initials. They generally appear on the interior of barrels, the top of ingots, or on handles of amphorae (figs. 1–2). The inscriptions are normally made with techniques that would last even if the object was reused several times. As André Tchernia⁴³ once suggested, it is more likely that the stamps served as a mark of control; for instance, if a whole batch of containers were to break due to their low quality, the owner (producer or trader) of the content could hold the manufacturer of the container liable for the loss of his

East (H. M. Cotton, R. G. Hoyland, J. J. Price, and D. J. Wasserstein, eds.; Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 2009); D. E. Trout, "Inscribing Identity: The Latin Epigraphic Habit in Late Antiquity," in *A Companion to Late Antiquity* (P. Rousseau, ed.; Sussex: Blackwell, 2009): 170–186; E. A. Meyer, "Explaining the Epigraphic Habit in the Roman Empire: The Evidence of Epitaphs," *JRS* 80 (1990): 74–96; idem, "Epigraphy and Communication," in *The Oxford Handbook of Social Relations in the Roman World* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2011): 191–226; idem, "Inscriptions As Honours and the Athenian Epigraphic Habit," *Historia: Zeitschrift für Alte Geschichte* 62.4 (2013): 453–505. Other authors have challenged MacMullen's theory; see, for example: F. Beltran Lloris, "The Epigraphic Habit in the Roman World," in *The Oxford Handbook of Roman Epigraphy* (C. Bruun and J. Edmonson, eds.; Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2014): 131–148, or J. Hahn, "Epigraphic Habit," in *The Encyclopaedia of Ancient History* (New York: Wiley-Blackwell, 2013): 2447–2448.

⁴² M. Corbier, *Donner à voir, donner à lire. Mémoire et communication dans la Rome ancienne* (Paris: CNRS, 2006): 70, 85; Meyer, *Epigraphy and Communication* (n 41): 198.

⁴³ A. Tchernia, "Les amphores romaines et l'histoire économique," *Journal des Savants* (1967): 231; however, the recent paper by X. Rubio Campillo et al., "Bayesian Analysis and Free Market Trade within the Roman Empire," *Antiquity* 91.359 (2017): 1250, still manifests doubts about the actual significance of the stamps.

product (D.13.6.18.3). In fact, a fresco from Ostia⁴⁴ (fig. D, appendix, Pl. XVII) depicts a trial scene where two subjects are in discussion around a broken amphora. The identity of the person in the fresco is unknown; it is unclear whether it was the carrier or the producer. It is clear that these containers could be brought as proof in a trial (D.22.4.1–2). The same reasoning could be applied to barrels, and it is interesting to see how the liability of the potter could be expressed in only these simple, permanent marks.

The stoppers were stamped for the obvious reason that the material employed accommodated that technique and its location, on the top of the amphorae or the side of the barrel,⁴⁵ and their writings identified the merchant.⁴⁶ The vessels were sealed when filled at the estate or kiln,⁴⁷ but they could be re-sealed at the boat with a material such as sand or clay into which the name of the merchant was stamped.⁴⁸

Painted inscriptions refer to the details of the sale agreement or the transport, like the features of the product or the merchant. The technique attests perfectly to its use, as it is visible, can be made after filling and sealing the container, and will last until the end of the trip; but it can still be cancelled and painted again in case of reuse.⁴⁹ In a broad sense, I would like to differentiate among the following models of painted merchandise:

1. Containers which were found in contexts related to shipping and transport. These artifacts normally have inscriptions related to: the product and its characteristics or quantity, the merchant, or

⁴⁴ C. Pavolini, *Ostia* (Rome: Guide Archeologiche Laterza, 1983): 197, fig. 4.1.

⁴⁵ A. Desbat, “Un bouchon de bois du I^{er} s. après J.-C. recueilli dans la Saône à Lyon et la question du tonneau à l’époque romaine,” *Gallia* 48 (1991): 319–336.

⁴⁶ Sometimes it could have been a merchant-shipper, as was affirmed since the discovery of the wreck Dramont A, in which the name of the stoppers (*Sexti Arrii*) was the same as the one on the anchor. P. A. Gianfrotta, “Note di epigrafia ‘marittima’. Aggiornamenti su tappi d’anfora, ceppi d’ancora e altro,” in *Epigrafia della produzione e della distribuzione. Actes de la VIIe Rencontre franco-italienne sur l’épigraphie du monde romain* (Rome, 5–6 juin 1992) (Rome: École Française de Rome, 1994): 591.

⁴⁷ See the papyri evidence underlined by Philip Mayerson, “Jar Stoppers and the Sealing of Winejars,” *ZPE* 136 (2001): 217–220.

⁴⁸ As can be demonstrated with the evidence of the seals found in shipwrecks such as M. Almagro, and B. Vilar Sancho, “Sello inédito de Madera hallado en el pecio del ‘Cap Negret’ (Ibiza),” *Rivista di Studi Liguri* 34 (1968): 323–336; D. Djaoui, “Découverte d’un double sceau en bois à date consulaire (épave de Tiboulon de Maire, Marseille). Étude préliminaire,” in *SFECAG. Actes Du Congrès d’Arles* (Arles: Decitre, 2011): 625–632.

⁴⁹ J. T. Peña. *Roman Pottery in the Archaeological Record* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 2007): 62.

features related to its transportation (e.g., *CIL*.XV.4692; *CIL*.IV.2588). Sometimes the containers carry inscriptions referring to their date of bottling, in the case of wine,⁵⁰ or of the aging, in the case of fish sauces.⁵¹ Both of them are hardly understandable (or legible) to anyone not involved in trade, and consequently used to that language. Wine vessels carry consular dates⁵² and fish sauces carry an inscription as “*A(nnorum)* [number of the years aging] *A(nnorum)*.” Inside group (1) we can find three sorts of artifacts which are made up of different kinds of objects:

- a. Objects which were employed in public supply, present details such as the product’s quantity or the merchant, but also sometimes bear inscriptions that witness the management of the cycle of distribution in which they were embedded. The name of the merchant or receiver would be written in visible places, such as the belly of an amphora, where it could be easily read by the crew of the ship who had to unload it and handle it for the interested parties. That is the case of the Dressel 20 amphorae, destined for the public supply, as *CIL* XV (e.g., fig. 6), or the marble destined for construction of public buildings.⁵³ Both types of goods present abbreviated forms of the controls and details about their registration, the meaning of which is still being discussed. These inscriptions were addressed to the subjects working on behalf of the Roman government to register and control them, and occur within a particular distribution itinerary. These encoded and abbreviated messages were understandable to the people involved in public trade, used to the abbreviated formulas.

⁵⁰ Some examples can be found in: J. P. Ballester. “Las ánforas Dressel 1 con datación consular. Una pieza de Cartagena,” *Saguntum: Papeles del Laboratorio de Arqueología de Valencia* 29 (1995): 175–186; M. Mongardi. “Tituli picti con datazione consolare su anfore vinarie italiche: indagini preliminari,” in *Instrumenta inscripta VI. Le iscrizioni con funzione didascalico-esplicativa* (M. Buora and S. Magnani, eds.; Trieste: Editreg, 2016): 101–129.

⁵¹ E.g., *CIL*.XV.4732–4733, 4753; *CIL*.IV.5605, 5607–5609; 2588; 5638, *inter alia*.

⁵² This is largely a matter of my interpretation, but the sale of wine was one of the varieties of sale that had more peculiarities, as for example tasting to check that the liquid was in a good state of preservation and had not turned into vinegar (D.18.2.9.2). For some literature, see n 39.

⁵³ See, for example, M. Christol and T. Drew-Bear, “Documents latins de Phrygie,” *Tyche* 1 (1986): 41–87; A. Hirt, *Imperial Mines and Quarries in the Roman World: Organizational Aspects 27 BC–AD 235* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2011); B. Russell, *The Economics of Roman Stone Trade* (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2013): 45–47.

Figure 6: *CIL.XV.4091*, inscription δ of Dressel 20 from Hadrian's era (second century C.E.).

- b. The *deigmata*, which consist of small vessels, closed with seals to prevent manipulations or changes that represent quality samples of grain transported by ship.⁵⁴ These pots can also act as a contract of transport, to be invoked in respect of customs officials' inspection of the foodstuff on arrival at the port. One of them (*CIL.IV.9591*),⁵⁵ consisting of a little grain amphora bears an inscription that can be translated as:

⁵⁴ O. Guéraud, "Deux documents relatifs au transport des céréales dans l'Égypte romaine," *Annales du service des antiquités de l'Égypte* 33 (1933): 59–64; idem, "Un vase ayant contenu un échantillon de blé (DEIGMA)," *Journal of Juristic Papyrology* 4 (1950): 107–115; B. Liou and M. Morel, "L'orge des Cavares: Une amphorette à inscription peinte trouvée dans le port antique de Marseille," *Revue Archéologique de Narbonnaise* 10 (1977): 189–197; D. C. Gofas, "La vente sur échantillon à Athènes d'après un texte d'Hypéride," in *Études d'Histoire du droit grec des affaires antiques, byzantin et post-byzantin* (Athens: Archaïologikî etaireia, 1995): 79–85; G. Casanova, "Campione: Testimonianze del vocabolo, con un papiro inedito," *Aegyptus: Rivista italiana di egiptologia e di papirologia* 75.1 (1995): 28–36; G. Geraci, "Mensura, pondus e probatio di stato nel rifornimento granario di Roma imperiale e di Costantinopoli," in *Politica retorica e simbolismo del primato: Roma e Costantinopoli (secoli IV–VII) atti del Convegno Internazionale (Catania, 4–7 Ottobre 2001): Omaggio a Rosario Soraci* (Catania: CULC, 2004): 155–181; A. Bresson, *L'économie de la Grèce des cités: Les espaces de l'échange* (Paris: Colin, 2008): 80; G. Geraci, "Sekomata e deigmata nei papiri come strumenti di controllo delle derrate fiscali e commerciali," in *Tout vendre, tout acheter. Structure et équipements des marchés antiques* (V. Chankowski, ed.; Paris: Ausonius, 2012): 347–363.

⁵⁵ The text has been subject to diverse editions, such as M. Della Corte, "Pompei. Scoperte epigrafiche (Reg. I, ins. VII–VIII e varie)," in *Notizie degli scavi di antichità* (1946): 112–117; R. Marichal and J. Dufour, "Paléographie latine et française," *École pratique des hautes études. 4e Section, sciences historiques et philologiques* 100.1 (1968): 295–316; A. Varone, "L'anforetta del grano," in *Nutrire l'impero. Storie di alimentazione da Roma e Pompei* (Rome: L'erma di Bretschneider, 2015): 21–22; J. Andreau, L. Rossi, and A. Tchernia, "*CIL IV, 9591: un transport de blé entre Ostie et Pompéi*," *Mélanges de l'École française de Rome—Antiquité* 129.1 (2017); E. Mataix Ferrandiz, "*CIL.IV.9591: Propuesta reconstructiva de los essentialia de una locatio conductio maritima*," in *Estudios homenaje al profesor Jose Remesal rodriguez* (V. Revilla, A. Aguilera Martin, and Ll. Pons Pujol, eds.; Barcelona: Instrumenta, 2019 forthcoming).

(On the one side) [written by one hand]

<p><i>Ante exemplar tr(itici) m(odiorum) XVCC in n(ave) cumba AMPRI de tutela Iovis et Iuno(nis) parasemi Victoria P(ubli) Pompili Saturi. Mag(ister) M(arcus) Lartidius Vitalis domo Clupeis</i></p>	<p>Sample sent with the cargo of 15,200 <i>modii</i> of grain, transported inside the ship <i>Cumba</i>, property of <i>Ampri</i>, after the protection of <i>Jupiter</i> and <i>Juno</i>, with the distinctive sign of victory, after the orders of <i>P. Pompilius Satorus</i>, <i>M. Lartidius Vitalis</i>, domiciled in <i>Clupea</i></p>
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(Under the belly) [written by another hand]

<p><i>Vect(ura) Ostis a [. . .] sol(ven)do gratis m(odios) CC S(olutio) F(acta) PR(ior) idus Octobr(es)</i></p>	<p>Cargo paid at <i>Ostia</i> and [. . .] solved. 200 <i>modii</i> are exempted of taxes <i>Solutio</i> performed before the <i>ides</i> of <i>October</i></p>
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(On the side)[written by another hand]

<p><i>Rustico /ab [. . .]</i></p>	<p>To <i>Rustico</i>⁵⁶ from [. . .]</p>
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⁵⁶ The names of the receivers normally appear written in the dative case (e.g., *CIL*.IV.5802), because it is chiefly used to indicate the person for whom an action takes place. See also, for example, the chart included in R. Etienne and F. Mayet, “Le Garum à la mode de Scaurus,” in *Alimenta: Estudios en homenaje al Dr. Michel Ponsich* (Gerión/Anejos 3; Madrid: Univ. Complutense de Madrid, 1991): 187–194; E. Marliere, L’autre et le tonneau dans l’Occident romain (Montagnac: Mergoïl, 2002): 63, 86; or L. Lagostena Barrios, “Las ánforas salsarias de Baetica. Consideraciones sobre sus elementos epigráficos,” in *Epigrafía Anfórica* (J. Remesal Rodríguez, ed.; Barcelona, Univ. de Barcelona, 2004): 197–220. On rare occasions the name cited in the genitive (*CIL*.IV.5675) can be identified as the clients, but generally the dative is the case employed to identify them. That is also affirmed by D. Bernal et al., “Urcei per salse di pesce da Pompei-Ercolano: una prima analisi,” in *Hornos, talleres y focos de producción alfarera en Hispania. II* (D. Bernal et al., eds.; Cádiz: Univ. de Cádiz, 2013): 275. As well, the use of the ablative implies the place where the product is addressed because this case is generally used to express motion away from something. These sorts of inscriptions appear on the external part of the object because they are linked to the transport of the object and they obviously need to be seen throughout the trip. It is usual to see them on objects that have to travel long distances and may at some point be passed from one carrier to another. Such is the case of one amphora

This epigraphic record provides elements of the transport such as the boat, the shipper, and the cargo with which the sample was travelling.⁵⁷ The second hand indicates the handling of the pot and the payment of the corresponding fee at a certain date. As can be appreciated, the text appears written by different hands and in different locations on the object. This points to three different moments of the distribution itinerary of the pot. The first inscription corresponds to the subjects writing it at the port of departure, detailing issues which would be read by the subjects registering it (second inscription), and finally the third inscription has information addressed to the final customer.

- c. Other samples meant to be sent and tasted by the potential customer to provide a sample of the product compose a third smaller group. Such is the case of a couple of jars found in Arles, one of olives⁵⁸ and another of wine,⁵⁹ displaying the name of the merchant or the vineyard's estate, and the amount of product available. Even if the information written on them was more succinct (e.g., Albani Valeri Proculi. 140 jars of 60 urns),⁶⁰ the text was addressed to one concrete individual who would understand what this abbreviated writing meant.

preserved in Lyon that reads VIENNAE/ T () IVLIO M [a?]CR [i?]INO and is probably linked to the transportation of the amphorae through the river system of the Rhone, which connected many cities in that region. See Silvino et al. (n 30): 653–654, fig.17.

⁵⁷ *CIL*.IV. 5894; P.Oxy. IV 708, dated to 188 c.E. describes the samples accompanying a cargo of grain.

⁵⁸ Djaoui, “Découverte d’un double sceau” (n 48).

⁵⁹ D. Djaoui and N. Tran, “Une cruche du port d’Arles et l’usage d’échantillons dans le commerce de vin romain,” *Mélanges de L’école Française de Rome. Antiquité* 126.2 (2014): 6–12.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, 2. Original text: ALB. VALER.PROCULI/ DOL.CXXXXX.SEXSAGENARIA. The grammatical case used when writing a name is essential to differentiate among merchant, producer, or receiver in the inscriptions. The genitive indicates (e.g., *Decimi Caecilii* in *CIL*.XV.3788; *CIL*.IV.9480) ownership and is used for inscriptions written on the external surface of the object, indicating the liability of the merchants for the quality of the goods sold. These names can be seen by the crew who need to differentiate the various merchants’ cargo (D.19.2.31) and it can be recognized by the receiver at the destination (P. Bad. 2.43). See, for example, the case of wrecks such as the ones of Port-Vendres 2, D. Colls et al., “L’épave Port-Vendres II et le commerce de la Bétique à l’époque de Claude,” *Archaeonautica* 1 (1977): 3–145; B. Liou and E. Rodriguez-Almeida, “Les inscriptions peintes des amphores du Pecio Gandolfo,” *Mélanges de L’école Française de Rome. Antiquité* 112.1 (2000): 7–25.

2. Finally there are containers used to preserve the product or found in domestic or market contexts. They display similar information to what can be found on the transport containers (product, quality, etc.), but written in different locations (e.g., *CIL.XV.4539; 4619; CIL.XIII.1008.47*) and sometimes referring to the quantity of the container. The difference might be because the contents were emptied from a bigger container, what probably happened in the warehouses of the port before reaching the market.⁶¹

Graffiti, in many cases, include a name in the genitive (possessive) case, an abbreviation of a personal name, a single letter, or a sign, such as a cross, triangle, or star (e.g., *CIL.XV.5295; CIL.IV.6251*).⁶² According to Peña, “some of the texts clearly served to indicate either the owner or owners of the vessel on which they appear or the person or persons entitled to use the vessel, and it seems a fair assumption that the bulk of the shorter texts and alphabetic signs were also created for this purpose.”⁶³ In the context of sea transport, graffiti seem to refer to people or issues that are secondary to the information painted (i.e., correspond to the contract of sale), but complement the epigraphic record of a vessel.⁶⁴ There is also some evidence of graffiti on the bottom of amphorae that was carried out at the pottery workshop, supposedly to indicate the number of containers made and the amount to be paid to the potter.⁶⁵ However, in domestic and market contexts, graffiti refer to details of the sale such as the product and weight of the container.⁶⁶ The objects found in these areas

⁶¹ See the case of the port of Marseille and the *dolia* warehouse of the *Pirani* family, which was connected to the docks, P. Arnaud. “Maritime Infrastructure: Between Public and Private Initiative,” in *Infrastruktur und Herrschaftsorganisationim Imperium Romanum* (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2012): 176.

⁶² One of the most complete references to vessels inscribed with this technique has been recently published, see Andrieu (N 3).

⁶³ Peña (N 49): 29.

⁶⁴ B. Galsterer, *Die Graffiti auf der romischen Gefasskeramik aus Haltern* (Munster: Aschendorff, 1983): 66–72; G. Garcia Brosa and P. Ozcariz Gil, “Los grafitos nominales de las ánforas Dressel 20: El caso del graffito *Vitalis*,” *Provinciae Imperii Romani inscriptionibus descriptae: Barcelona, 3–8 septembris 2002: Acta* (Giulia Baratta and Alejandra Guzmán Almagro, eds.; Barcelona: Institut d’Estudis Catalans, 2007): 549–554.

⁶⁵ F. Pallares, “La nave romana del golfo di Diano Marina, Relazione preliminare della campagna 1981,” *Forma Maris Antiqui XI–XII* (1975–1981): 90–91, fig.16; Gavini (N 31): 240, fig. 9.

⁶⁶ Starting with an early example from the Athenian agora, which is indicative of the use of this “graffiti habit,” see M. L. Lawall, “Graffiti, Wine Selling, and the Reuse of Amphoras in the Athenian Agora, ca. 430 to 400 B.C.,” *Hesperia* 69.1 (2000): 3–90; R. Bortollin and B. Bruno, “Il graffito ‘melis’ su un vaso di Arcole (VR). Considerazioni sui

present abbreviated inscriptions such as TP (*testa pondo*), meaning the total weight of the container, which normally did not appear on vessels used in transport, since it referred to the quantity bought by the customer.⁶⁷ In the case of barrels, graffiti rarely appear on the exterior,⁶⁸ and also normally display names, thus referring to the ownership of the object. Generally speaking, the inscriptions written with this technique represent informal messages written by the parties in contact with the artifact.

Graffiti were commonly applied on metal artifacts (e.g., labels, ingots), but it is possible to differentiate among techniques: the ingots refer to production with a stamp on top, and to the diverse transfers of the object to different owners with etched graffiti. This is the reason we find ingots marked on several occasions.⁶⁹ Concerning lead labels, we also have to differentiate those that refer to production⁷⁰ from the ones that refer to a treatment applied to a product, such as those generally found in the context of the *fullonica*, or dry-cleaners.⁷¹ The latter refer to treatments applied to the product and the name of the owner and correspond to a contract of provision of service (*locatio conductio operis*).⁷² Despite

contenitori da miele nell'antichità," in *Scritti di archeologia in ricordo di Giovanna Luisa Ravagnan* (E. Bianchin Citton and M. Tirelli, eds.; Treviso: Dossan, 2006): 113–124; R. Bortollin, *Archeologia del miele* (Mantova: Societa Archeologica, 2008): 176–180, where in the catalogue the author distinguishes between transport and preservation containers; also C. Corti, "Il peso delle anfore. Alcune osservazioni sulle indicazioni didascaliche graffite e le modalità di pesatura," *Atti del VI incontro instrumenta inscripta, Aquileia (26–28 marzo 2015)* (M. Buora and S. Magnani, eds.; Antichità Altoadriatiche 83; Trieste: Editreg, 2016): 159–176.

⁶⁷ *CIL*.XIII.1008.43; *L'Année épigraphique* 1966.236; 1994.1247; 2006.498c.

⁶⁸ Marliere (N 56): 63, 86.

⁶⁹ For the logic of the processes, see Rico (N 40); and for some examples of ingots marked in different occasions, P. Aratta, "Un relitto da Cala Rossano (Ventotene). Tituli picti su anfore e bollo su lingotti di stagno," *Publications de l'ecole française de Rome* 193.1 (1994): 477–496; C. De Juan Fuertes et al., "El precio Bou Ferrer (La Vila Joiosa-Alicante). Nuevos datos sobre su cargamento y primeras evidencias de la arquitectura naval," in *Arqueología subacuática española: Actas del I Congreso de Arqueología Náutica y Subacuática Española, Cartagena, 14, 15 y 16 de marzo de 2013, 1* (Cartagena: UCA, 2014): 113–124.

⁷⁰ B. Rocco, "Nuovi piombi mercantili della Sicilia greca," *Sicilia Archeologica* 14 (1971): 27–36; R. Lequément, "Étiquettes de plomb sur les amphores d'Afrique," *Mélanges de L'ecole Française de Rome. Antiquité* 87.2 (1975): 667–680.

⁷¹ Some publications about the topic are, A. Buonopane and E. Buchi, "Le etichette plumbee rinvenute a Feltre: aspetti onomastici, lessicali, economici e tecnici," in *I territori della via Claudia Augusta: incontri di archeologiae* (Trento: TEMI, 2005): 43–51; L. A. Hidalgo et al., "Étiquetas comerciales de plomo para textiles en Augusta Emerita," in *Textiles, cestería y tintes en el mundo mediterráneo antiguo* (Valencia: Univ. de Valencia, 2016): 221–237.

⁷² D.7.1.13.8; D.19.2.25.8. Concerning the functioning of the dry-cleaners, see M. Flohr,

the fact that these labels are not connected with seaborne trade, they are mentioned here as an example of the techniques used in the context of a shop and in relation to the other stamped labels linked with maritime shipping.

In the epigraphy of merchandise, the inscriptions appear shortened and written in a hasty way, making them difficult to understand for both ancient and current readers.⁷³ Once their meaning is deciphered, it becomes clear that the writings refer to details associated with trade and transport. They were understood by people working in commerce, who were aware of the meaning and goals of such abbreviated writings. This lexicon allowed a remote dialogue to take place between producers, intermediaries, and consumers, as well as established a communication code that was understandable within the commercial world where these objects functioned. Every term or abbreviation used in these inscriptions delivered a distinct and unique message, often reflecting the inner organization or agreements formalised during the trade operations.

VI. CONCLUSION: LIFE CYCLE OF AN OBJECT ACCORDING TO ITS EPIGRAPHIC RECORD

For these final remarks, I would like to bring back the concept of “sense of audience.” With that, I want to affirm that these commercial inscriptions were written in a determinate way to recall the attention of the parties associated with trade. The language and information written on the objects display data addressed to a concrete audience, being the subjects involved in trade and transportation at Roman ports. Also, differences in the calligraphic style and abbreviations used reveal different distribution patterns and codes used by people involved in trade to help the merchandise reach its destination. Consequently, even if encoded, they were understood by the people involved in the procedures of trade or transportation of the merchandise.

The repetition of certain patterns in the techniques, position, and language, but also of the procedures performed during the commercial cycle, allowed the parties involved in trade identify the context of each

The World of the Fullo: Work, Economy, and Society in Roman Italy (Oxford: Oxford Univ., 2013).

⁷³ The problem is highlighted for example by A. Aguilera Martín, “La normalisation de l’épigraphie amphorique: Les tituli picti des amphores dressel 20,” in *Inscriptions mineures: Nouveautés et réflexions. Actes du premier colloque Ductus, 19–20 juin 2008, Université de Lausanne* (M. E. Fuchs, R. Sylvestre, and C. Smith Heidenreich, eds.; Bern: Haftad, 2012): 135–143.

inscription. As the evidence indicates, sometimes a technique was dependent on the features of the material, as the creator was trying to make a lasting inscription which would have been visible all along the distribution path. These marks helped to keep track of the merchandise and ensured that it arrived at its destination. The evidence further suggests that techniques, such as stamps or marks made with fire, were intended to remain permanently on the object, as they reflected the liability of the producer for the quality of the artifact, which had to be preserved during the trip. Painted inscriptions reflected the essential elements of the sale and transport contracts in which these objects were involved. These kind of agreements were consensual, what meant that Roman law already set out the essential parts of a contract,⁷⁴ but the particularities of each sale contract lay on the will of the parties. That is the reason why we can find certain essential elements repeated (e.g., merchant, product), but also some additions that depended on the product sold and the will of the parties (e.g., consular date for the wine).

It is possible then to speak about a “graffiti habit”⁷⁵ in relation with the epigraphic habit theory that I have used to understand Roman merchandise. These texts include data of secondary importance for the sale or transportation of objects in the context of long-distance trade and details written by the parties in domestic or market contexts. Graffiti was a technique which seemed to appeal to a narrow audience, being used to inscribe personal and spontaneous messages. Thus they indicate details such as the ownership of a vessel, or details of a sale in the case of containers used for preservation. Graffiti alone deserve a more in depth study, because they still reveal information about literacy and localized practices, despite the fact that it seems that their “sense of audience” is lower than other techniques such as stamp or paint.⁷⁶

As I hope to have demonstrated, there is more to the epigraphic record on merchandise than meets the eye. The relationship between the inscriptions written on an artifact hide a range of phenomena related to the

⁷⁴ D. Johnston. *Roman Law in Context* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ., 1999): 78.

⁷⁵ The term, obviously recalling the seminal paper of MacMullen already cited in N 2, has been labelled by Polly Lohmann, who has focused on the graffiti on the walls of Pompeii. P. Lohmann, “Some Thoughts on the Habits of Graffiti-Writing: Visual Aspects of Scratched Inscriptions within Pompeian Houses,” in *Seen and Unseen Spaces* (M. Dalton; G. Peters; and A. Tavares, eds.; Cambridge: ARC 30.1, 2015): 70–76.

⁷⁶ The only comprehensive study of this kind undertaken to date is Evans’ analysis of a corpus of ca. four hundred vessels bearing one or more *post-cocturam* graffiti recovered at a large number of excavated sites across Britain. See J. Evans. “Graffiti and the Evidence of Literacy and Pottery Use in Roman Britain,” *Archaeological Journal* 144.1 (1987): 191–204.

political economy, monopolies, property, and liability that originate in the agreements made among the parties involved. As with every model, these characterizations leave out some particularities of concrete cases. However, the description of the distribution cycle, and the different aims of the techniques used in the inscriptions help provide a scheme to understand the mind-set of the merchants. The codes and abbreviations employed indicated that these subjects were aware of the practical scope of these inscriptions. In this way, these inscriptions and their distinctive features were metapragmatic, as they were useful for the traders and people associated with commerce.

APPENDIX

Figure A: Chart showing the materials analysed in this study.

Type of inscription	Label given	Refers to
Product	A	Kind of good
Quality	B1	Nature of the good
Qualitative	B2	Features of the good referring to maturation or origin
Seller	D	Trader
Weight or measure	C	Amount of the good traded
Weight or measure	α (Dressel 20)	Amount of the good traded
Weight or measure	γ (Dressel 20)	Amount of the good traded
Seller	β (Dressel 20)	Trader
General inscription	F	Data about the agreement (transport details, receiver, sale conditions)
Production	P	Production
Control	δ (Dressel 20)	Control of goods addressed to public supply

Figure B: Chart indicating the different kinds of inscriptions found on the artifacts.

Support	Technique	Location	Message
Amphora/ Jug	Painted	On the side of the neck or belly/on the neck or belly/on the bottom/on the shoulder*	Elements linked to the features of the product sold, the transport and the registration
Amphora/ Jug	Stamped	On the handle/on the bottom/on the rim	Producer
Amphora/ Jug	Graffiti post- <i>cocturam</i>	On the side of the neck or belly/on the side of the neck or belly/on the neck or belly	Details linked to the sale of the product
Amphora/ Jug	Graffiti pre- <i>cocturam</i>	On the handle/on the bottom	Probably marks linked to the production process
Barrel	Chiselled	Exterior/Interior	Merchant/producer
Barrel	Marked with fire	Exterior/Interior	Merchant/producer
Barrel	Painted	Exterior/Interior	Elements linked to the features of the product sold, the transport/producer
Barrel	Graffiti	Exterior/Interior	Elements linked to the features of the product sold/producer
Ingot	Stamped	On the top/on the side	Producer
Ingot	Graffiti	On the side/on the base	Merchant/receiver/details of the storage
Marble	Chiselled	On the side	Details of the transport/registration
Stopper	Stamped	Along the object	Merchant

Figure C: Techniques and positions of the inscriptions on the objects.

* That case concretely appears in the Greek amphorae found in the Athenian agora, see Lang (n 6): 55–86.

Figure D: Fresco with judicial scene from the Caseggiato del'Ercole, a market building at Ostia, dating to second century C.E.
(*Photograph by Emilia Mataix Ferrándiz*)⁷⁷

⁷⁷ Pavolini, *Ostia* (n 44): 197, fig. 4.1.

PLATE XVI

Figure 1: Examples of different inscribed artifacts and techniques. From left to right: painted fish sauce amphora from Almeria; barrel stave with fire marks from Vindolanda; graffiti in amphora found in Magdalensberg (Germany).

Figure 2: Dressel 20 seal impressions and inscriptions from the Severan period (Second half 2nd c. C.E. and first half 3rd c. C.E.).

PLATE XVII

Figure D: Fresco with judicial scene from the Casggiato del'Ercole, a market building at Ostia, dating to second century C.E.

(Photograph by Emilia Mataix Ferrándiz)